

EVOLVABLE BELIEVABLE AGENTS FOR BROADCASTED INTERACTIVE GAME SHOWS

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Abstract

The possibility of interactive digital shows creation at a cost comparable with the creation of 2D web pages is discussed in the present paper. The reduction of cost is due to several reasons. 1) Reduction of bandwidth. The mathematical model of the network is discussed in some detail. 2) A further reduction of cost is described. This is made possible by using an asymmetrical channel that uses data broadcasting for 'one-to-many' communication and the Internet for one-to-one. 3) The creation of believable characters by means of artificial life techniques. The internal model of the characters is described along with the theoretical foundations of the techniques used for the character evolvability. A simple interactive interface allows show-developers, as well as participants in shows to cast their own characters without the need of programming. The characters will also continue to evolve indefinitely. Finally, the game show is only a testbed for the technology that could be used for other types of shows as well.

1 Introduction

In that paper we will discuss how we have studied the possibility of "broadcasted interactive games shows" creation. In particular, we will focus on the role of "evolvable believable agents." The discussion of some details on how we have implemented the air and satellite broadcasting of digital game shows will also be given.

The need of evolvable believable agents in games shows comes from the increasing demand of such type of entertainment along with the possibility to exploit to full extent both the interactivity of computers linked to a network and the intrinsic lower bandwidth of the implementation of shows that makes use of digital characters.

The concept of the "believable agent" has been introduced in (Bates, 1994) and our approach to collaborative evolutionary systems has been derived from Dawkins Biomorphs (Dawkins, 1986).

Real game shows has been, historically among the first entertainment shows to be broadcasted by television.

What does "digital play" mean in the framework of the Amusement project? The answer, that comes at the end of a long historical evolution of the entertainment culture, is simple. Bring the best of the past (mostly the possibility of interaction among spectators and between spectators and actors) along with the best of modern technology (namely the possibility of interaction at a distance).

Normally, in a game show, there are three types of fundamental roles: players, a conductor and the audience. The audience can be divided, in turn, into two groups: in site audience and at home audience. This was an "escamotage", implemented since the beginning of the TV era, aimed at solving the dicotomy

of having an interactive audience that could be able, for example, to make an applause, (such an audience must have been in the same physical site of the players) and a vast audience (that may have been everywhere else). Now it is worth noticing that the crowd sitting in even the world biggest stadium is order of magnitude smaller than an average TV audience. The trade off was hence, to have both one interactive (and small in size) and one larger (and completely passive) audiences. Today it is possible to have an audience both large and interactive at the same time. In the digital age we have another advantage that has been somehow overlooked.

Today it is possible not only to convert an analog image of a show into a digital stream of bits, as today's digital TV normally does (the relevant information is, strictly technically speaking, digital, of course, but, logically, the information is organized, simply, as an "analog" of the real play, since they do nothing more than replicate the image of the real play), but also to create, as we do in the Amusement project, a digital show directly from scratch using digital actors.

In the Amusement project a digital play is created from scratch using digital actors as discussed in the following passages.

The digital actors and the environment are replicated only once, at the beginning, in all the "clients" and all that needs to be re-transmitted is their "dynamics."

This type of approach lowers tremendously the bandwidth, reducing it by orders of magnitude. In section 4.3 a mathematical model of the network requirements is described. The associated cost of such a transmission will be so low that an entire new class of productions is now possible. For example, even elementary schools can easily raise the few hundred dollars necessary to transmit worldwide a digital play.

Much in the same way that now almost anybody can publish written text and 2D images whereas before he had to rely on the press and a publisher. This sort of democratization of the press is now possible for the entertainment industry as well. We are at the edge of a new "Gutenberg Galaxy" to paraphrase McLuhan's words. (McLuhan, 1962.) We have in the Amusement project four thousand Italian schools already equipped with the receiving hardware and software and ready to begin the productions. Those schools will be the first but of course, not the only audience of the said productions. The game show has been proposed as a valuable tool for what is now called "edutainment" that is "educational-entertainment").

In order to maintain this possibility of economic game show production, anyhow the digital characters, that are intrinsically cheap to be broadcasted need also to be programmed in a non expensive way.

On the other hand, people expect, from shows in general, the vast richness of characters that cartoons, if not real actors, have let us to be used to. One possible solution is, hence, to program into the characters some sort of "artificial life."

In the Amusement project we have successfully applied "collaborative evolvable procedures" to let the users of a game cast the gestures that they want their avatars to show in the game itself. This type of technique can be applied not only to closed group interactive games, as is the case, for example, of networked computer games, but also to true broadcasted game shows.

2 Implementation of the Collaborative System

How does this happen? First of all, the game can be played between avatars (behind whom there are real players), or between avatars and "bots" (behind whom there are artificial life computer programs).

Anyhow, most of the time they also need a conductor, or moderator of the game. Even in the case in which the game is very well structured and, hence, the conductor can be efficiently implemented as a deterministic "classical" AI algorithm, Artificial Life technique can be used to let its behavior be a "believable character." (Bates, 1994) For example, in the Amusement project the gestures of any character are not defined beforehand, but they evolve genetically. In particular, hence, the gestures of the conductors can be triggered by an internal model relevant to the "algorithm of the game," but they will not always be the same since they are evolving throughout the game. For example, a gesture welcoming new participants, will never be the same in all the game instances. Moreover, the participants themselves will not need to (explicitly) program the gestures needed in the game. This allows them to be concentrated on the game itself. At the same time their expressiveness can be very rich, because they can easily, starting from a first set of default gesture genes, evolve their own gesture sets. In fact, using as selective pressure their preferences for some gesture instead of some others, their gesture set

will evolve allowing effectiveness in communicating and or disguising their real moods during the game.

Moreover, the association of a given situation (say, the proximity to an other avatar or an object) to a given gesture can be regarded as a behavior (Kosko, 1992). This association in the Amusement project models is controlled by a genome and hence, is susceptible to evolution itself.

Of special interest to those of us in the world of games and entertainment, is the fact that showing the user's real mood can be counter-productive. In order to provide an avatar with the ability to hide emotions whenever it is necessary, we have allowed the user to define their real mood along with the mood that they want to simulate. The resulting avatar's expression and actions will depend on how gifted it is in dissimulating. The association of a real mood and the expressed mood is controlled in the Amusement implementation, by means of a deterministic, albeit "fuzzy logic" internal model.

The core of the authoring tool generating the gesture by means of evolutionary technique is described in sections 4.1 and 4.2 whereas in section 4.3 we will discuss the details of the broadcasting of interactive game shows.

3 Technical description of the system

In the following a detailed description of the system will be given. The system has been implemented making use of existing interactive virtual worlds' platforms as well as original proprietary technologies. The general cabled networked architecture has been tested using existing commercial or experimental virtual world platforms. The evolutionary engine is a proprietary software source coded in C. The data broadcasting part makes use of proprietary hardware and technologies. Broadcast data transmissions are delivered by Italian state owned channel RAI3 (freq. 11.534 GHz pol. V) on Hot Bird 1, 13 degree east.

It is needed an analog satellite receiver with radiofrequency output (UHF) tunable on standard terrestrial channels (e.g. channel 21 or 45 or 52); analog satellite receivers with fixed (or trimmable) output. Channel 36 cannot be used. It is better to use at least a 90 cm diameter dish, with 0.8 dB (or better) noise figure LNB.

3.1 Our approach to "intelligent behavior"

Our approach to "intelligent behavior" is based on the chapter "Intelligent Behavior As Adaptive Model-Free Estimation" found in (Kosko, 1992.)

In Kosko's view (the notation is slightly different from Kosko's), a behavior (b), defined as a correspondence between a given situation (or stimulus) ($s \in S$) and a response ($r \in R$), can be modeled as a function b that maps S onto R, being S the set of all the possible Stimuli, and R the set of all the possible Responses. That is:

$$b : S \rightarrow R$$

Regardless of the complexity of the dynamics linking the input (situation) to the output (response), at the most abstract level, it is possible to think of a behavior as a mapping between pairs of vectors (s, r). The correspondence is usually obtained by means of a neural network or a fuzzy system. We have used Fuzzy Associative Memories (FAMs). Hence in our work b is a FAM matrix. The genome generating the matrix b evolves by cumulative selection of small changes analogously to what is described in (Dawkins, 1986) for the morphology of artificial creatures. R is usually called gestures. R also evolves by means of a similar procedure. The user, or the game developer, first uses an interactive procedure of the type described in (Dawkins, 1986) in order to cast the set of gestures needed and hence, by means of a similar procedure the mapping b .

One of the advantages of this approach is that it is model-free. This is particularly useful given the complexity of the task of modelling intelligent behavior. Modeling intelligent behavior, moods and emotions is extremely interesting, but it is out of the scope of this paper.

The term “model-free” should not be taken too literally. What is really model-free is the b function. Some sort of modeling (dimensions of input/output spaces, for example) is obviously necessary.

3.2 How Evolution Arises from Avatars Interaction

Avatars who are in our Active Worlds’ world “Amuse” and “Amuse 2” move driven by users instructions (via mouse or other pointing devices) or by internal logic or both, depending on the functioning mode selected. We have defined three different modes called mode 1, 2 or 3 respectively. Except for debugging and experimental purposes their mode is not shown to the user.

Regardless of the functioning mode, the pointing device acts only as global moving device. The user can direct only the global displacement of its avatar and not the movement of its single parts (for example, the expression of “moods” via a predefined, but evolvable gesture or the walking style pattern).

The behavior (i.e. response to a given situation) is completely determined by both the internal state of the avatar and the situation. I.e., if one avatar moves towards another it is up to the user’s avatar, to decide whether or not to greet the other avatar and how.

3.2.1 Mode 1 (Puppet Mode)

In this Mode, avatars are driven by user’s pointing device commands in order to interact with other avatars. Evolution is still possible for the avatars functioning in this mode but, the outcomes of the evolution will not show until their mode is switched to an higher mode. Anyhow, they will influence both of the avatar’s behavior, in the short term, (i.e. they make other avatars react in a certain way) and the evolution of behavior in the long term (i.e. they way they react to a given situation).

PUPPET

Provided the others are functioning in modes 2 and 3, the influence of mode 1 on mode 2 and of mode 1 on mode 3 will be soon visible. This is mainly a test and a training mode.

3.2.2 Mode 2 (Ro-Bot Mode)

In Mode 2 the avatar accepts no direct pointing device input. It acts according to its internal state and the interaction with other avatars.

(RO)BOT

3.2.3 Mode 3 (Dog Mode)

In this Mode the user merely suggests, by means of a pointing device, what the avatar should do (i.e. pointing towards a given direction or goal). The avatar,

in turn, interprets the command and decides how to do the task (in other terms he can “choose how to get there, how to walk and what to do in the meantime.”) In principle its freedom could arrive even up to the point of ignoring the user’s command. We have not implemented such a mode insofar. We have called it high 3 mode. We have implemented only low 3 mode up to now.

A more formal discussion of the internal model follows.

3.2.4 Formal discussion of the internal model

The generic internal model is illustrated in figure 1. In order to explain the workings of the internal model, we will describe it from the point of view of a generic user.

The user sees the avatar’s physical appearance, the displacements and rotations of its whole body *inside* the environment. Such displacements and rotations are called *movements*. Moreover, the user can see the rotations of the various body segments of the avatar. A given set of such rotations is called a *gesture*. During a session in a Virtual World what the user perceives is a combination between movements and gestures.

The user, in turn, can interact with both the environment and the avatar by means of a generic pointing device.

The model has also an internal state that, for the sake of simplicity, we have limited in this first part of the Amusement project to the following variables: x, y, z, p (three cartesian coordinates of the avatar’s position plus the angle of pointing). The model accepts two sub-sets of inputs: the user inputs (\underline{USR}), and the other avatar position and pointing (\overline{USR}). The transition from one state to the next is regulated by the clock CK1. The CK1 frequency is usually a sub-multiple of the framerate. The framerate is usually a sub-multiple of the framerate. The framerate is 10 fr/s. The CK1 frequency is usually 1 Hertz, i.e. 1 every 10 frames. The outputs are generated from the inputs by means of four fundamental functions called IO, SO, IS, SS. The gestures are selected from an ordered, finite cardinality, set by the output by means of the OG function. The output from IO and SO, and from IS and SS, is compounded by means of the operator which does not necessarily have to be a sum.

The structure of IO, SO, IS, SS can be diversified and we will discuss only the implementations that are relevant to our application.

Before proceeding we will introduce some little modifications to the model adopted in figure 1. The relevant schematic diagram is illustrated in figure 2.

In this new version the two sub-sets of the input, \underline{USR} and \overline{USR} , have been made explicit. Moreover, the following transforms have been applied, taking into account only the "horizontal" coordinates x and z. The vertical y coordinate is ignored.

The variable t is the total time of interaction and is calculated by summing the CK1 intervals where d and ϕ are defined as follows:

$$\phi = \rho_2 - \rho_1$$

$$d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 - (z_2 - z_1)^2}$$

3.2.5 Modes in detail

The simplest case of all is the one we have called *mode 1* (puppet mode, figure 3). In this case SG and SS are null. The link between the output and the input is, hence, direct. The next state, that is the next avatar position and pointing, is specified directly from the user input as well as the the predefined gesture to be performed.

In *mode 2* the avatar is, in reality, a fully independent agent usually called a BOT (taken from the well known word “robot”). The BOT is fully independent and the user has no *direct* way to interact with it. The output and, hence, the relevant gestures, are function of the state by means of SO only. The next state (in practice the next avatar position and pointing), is calculated as a function SS of the position of all the other avatars and/or the present avatar position.

In *low mode 3* the user specifies directly the next avatar

state (in practice the new avatar’s coordinates), but the gesture is calculated using the state of the avatar. In *high mode 3* the user can still specify directly the next avatar state. But, since now the function SS is present, the new state is a combination of both the user input and the avatar’s “will”.

The OG block has been made explicit in all modes for the following important reasons.

The OG is, among other things, the memory in which the gestures are stored, regardless on how they have been triggered and/or generated. The SO block is responsible of one the most important parts of the avatar model: the link between a situation, identified

with what we have defined here as the “state of the avatar”, and a gesture. We will call this association between the situation and the gesture a "behavior" according to (Kosko, 1992). The SO block implements the behavior function b.

3.3 Broadcasting Architecture

The Amusement center has been implemented with a distributed client server architecture. The architecture is truly distributed in the sense that all the different functionalities of the server can be (and, in fact, are) distributed on different Computers, that can be addressed by different IPs, and can be (and, in fact, are) physically distributed at different geographic locations.

FF = FORGET FUNCTION = TAKE LAST P/R ONLY (DONT QUEUE)

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In the Amusement project the Amusement center server (in the following called for short, simply the Server) is at the most abstract level possible a system with these basic functionalities:

1. Get the information from all users (functionality mode: Many to One).
2. Relay to all users the information generated by all the other users (functionality mode: Many to Many).

In the Amusement project the Amusement center client (in the following called for short simply the Client) is at the most abstract level possible a system with these basic functionalities:

1. Transmit the locally generated information to the Server (functionality mode: One to One).
2. Receive from the Server the information generated from all the other users (functionality mode: One to One).
3. “Render” the information in graphical acoustical and textual modes.

3.3.1 Network Logical description and principles of operation

The logical structure of the network is illustrated in the following block diagram figure 7.

The system is based on a distributed *synchronized* data base. The data base contains the following type of information on both the *avatars* and the *environment*:

- 1) Geometry
 - 1.a Avatar geometry
 - 1.b Environment geometry
- 2) Textures
 - 2.a Avatar textures
 - 2.b Environment textures
- 3) Avatar Gestures
- 4) Environment Sounds

The location of the central data base can be anywhere on the Internet (at an address specified by the world administrator). A cache image of the central data base is maintained at any client location. When the client is started, the data base "engine" (of the client), loads data into the rendering "engine" (of the client) from the cached image sending messages to the central data base for update. If no update is needed (i.e. the two data bases are synchronized) the rendering client uses only the cached data. The cached data are relevant only to the "static data", the dynamic data are transmitted through the Internet in the following way.

The rendering client, upon a user request of: translation, rotation or any other attribute change (of an object) sends an update request to the server program. Note that the server program doesn't need to be running on the same machine as the central data base nor does it even have to be close to it. Indeed they usually are far apart.

The server program address is identified by a universe data base, maintained by a universe administrator. When a legal, authorized server program is started, on any location on the Internet, the server program asks the universe specified in its ini file to be identified by means of its (that is the server program's) IP address and update the universe data base of IP addresses from which legal authorized worlds are operating.

3.3.1.1 Network requirements

3.3.1.1.1 Standard Cabled Internet Hypothesis

3.3.1.1.1.1 Analytical description from example of (simulated) Update data traffic

In order to illustrate the kind of parameters it has to be taken into account in order to estimate the dimensional requirements of a networking able to support the gaming in the Amusement project, an example of a simulated situation of the traffic is reported in the following graphs.

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First, we will simulate the traffic of Update Requests flowing from clients (towards the server) as illustrated in the first four graphs. The relevant resulting traffic entering the server is illustrated in the last one. The traffic is organized in quanta of constant size.

In the figures the quantum is normalized at the value of one arbitrary unit¹. At any given time that traffic of Update Requests entering the server is the sum of all the relevant traffic coming out from the clients. (as can be seen in the example figure the traffic from the clients can be zero for many contiguous intervals of time).

The relevant mathematical relationships are reported in the following equation where:

Ctur(t) [Client Traffic of Update Requests] is the traffic of Update Requests flowing from clients at any given time t.

Stur(t) [Server Traffic of Update Requests] is the traffic of Update Requests entering the server at any given time t.

N is the number of clients

$$Stur(t) = \sum_i Ctur_i(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.1}]$$

As can be seen, the traffic coming out from the rendering client to the server program is very low, being relevant only to translation and/or rotation of avatars.

The relevant traffic, seen from the server, is rather high, albeit still growing less² than linearly with the number of clients, as shown in [eq 1] and illustrated in the figures.

¹ In reality the dimension of the quantum is three reals for XYZ coordinates of position and four real for quaternions [quaternions] of rotation. The quaternions can be reduced from four to two since two out of three rotations are (usually) zero being the only usual whole body rotation around the vertical axis only. The triplet of position coordinates can be reduced to the couple of horizontal position coordinates since movement in the vertical direction is rare. The record is usually organized as follows [Length of PositionInfo, PositionInfo, Length of RotationInfo, RotationInfo]

² Less than linearly for the following reasons

1. The client receiving the update from all the other clients filters them in a way such he retains meaningful only the most recent one. We may call this function Forget Function or FF. The aim of the FF is to use only the most recent update. Of course if many intermediate updates are lost the movement of the object will be "jerky". Anyhow this strategy prevents the system to be overloaded and eventually stalled.
2. Not all the N clients are sending update requests at the same time.

On the other side of the net, the server program receives the sum of all clients update request, queues them and re-send, as updates, a copy of all of the updates to all the clients (that he knows that are running on its world). The situation here is dramatic since now the growth is exponential with respect to the number of clients N.

The relevant mathematical relationships are reported in the following equation where:

Stup(t) [Server Traffic of Updates] is the total traffic of Updates copies exiting from server at any given time t.

N is the number of clients

$$Stup(t) = N \cdot \sum_i Ctur_i(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.2a}]$$

The traffic flow dimensioning formulas can hence label the logical block diagram as follows:

Finally it can be noticed that the traffic entering the client equals the sum of all the update requests (coming from all the clients including itself). Formally:

Ctup(t) [Client Traffic of Updates] is the total traffic of Updates entering any client at any given time t.

N is the number of clients

$$Ctup(t) = \sum_i Ctur_i(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.3}]$$

Using [eq. 1] [eq.3] can be written as

$$Ctup(t) = Stur(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.4}]$$

[eq. 4] means that the traffic of updates entering any single client coincides with the total traffic entering (not coming out) the server (at any given time t). The traffic coming out from the server is much higher as seen in [eq. 2a].

3.3.1.1.1.2 Analytical description from example of (simulated) Object data traffic

The very first time a client logs into a world it requests to the central object database all the information needed for rendering both the environment and the avatars, hence copies them in a cache directory on the same client computer, as described in section two. The traffic happens to be "occasional" and hence occurs in "bursts". The bursts are of the same size of the central object database. Since this traffic occurs only the very first time a client logs into a world, albeit large in peak size (intensity), its time average at the central object database server is really low. In fact the probability that a logon is the logon of a new user is really low (after the world start up period). A simulated example is reported below³.

³ Traffic to clients is normalized to 1 arbitrary unit. Typical world Object database size 10Mb. Amusement Estimated Object database size 30Mb.

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A formal discussion follows

Let $Stor(t)$ [Server Traffic of Central Objects Data Base Requests] be the traffic of Central Objects Data Base Requests coming out of the Central Objects Data Base server at any given time t .

$Cto_i(t)$ [Client Traffic of Objects Data (from Central Data Base)] be the traffic of Objects Data Data entering the client upon request at any given time t (equals the size of Central Objects Database).

N be the total number of clients

$P_N(t)$ be the probability that N clients will be logging in for their very first time at any given time t (zero for large t intervals).

Hence we may write

$$Stor(t) = P_N(t) \cdot N \cdot Cto_i(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.5}]$$

3.3.1.1.2 Mixed Cabled Internet-Air Broadcast Hypothesis

As shown in the following figure 11 the update link on the cabled Internet can be substituted by an "air" Broadcast link.

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The "air" Broadcast link can be either via terrestrial VBI as in the previous figure 11 or via satellite as illustrated in the following figure 12.

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From the logic of the system the two solutions can be regarded as identical and the formal discussion of traffic follows:

$Stup(t)$ [Server Traffic of Updates] is the total traffic of Updates copies exiting from server at any given time t .

N is the number of clients

$$Stup(t) = \sum_i Ctur_i(t) \quad i = 1 \text{ to } N \quad [\text{eq.2b}]$$

In [eq.2b] it can be seen the dramatic increase in efficiency from the case of [eq.2a]. This is due to the drop in the growing rate (of the update traffic exiting the server) falling from exponential back to linear.

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As far as the individual client authorization procedures are concerned this version of the system is equally (if not more) safe than in the standard situation, because the client receivers will be abilitated, via a hardware based encryption system that can be remotely activated via password release, for any single service/world on an individual basis in real time by the universe and or world manager. All the described procedure will be completely transparent for both the system manager and the user.

The logical block diagram⁴ can be now labeled as follows:

⁴ It is shown only the case of terrestrial VBI since from this point of view both situations are identical

“Evolvable believable agents” has been successfully used in the Amusement Project in order to implement the Avatars and the non participating characters used in our broadcasted interactive game shows. The advantages that have been illustrated in this paper. As a conclusion we will just emphasize that the new “Gutenberg galaxy” (McLuhan, 1962) will be accessible only if an high degree of automation in the production of the shows can be attained. This can be regarded as the ideal continuation of the process begun with the automation of the printing process at the time of Gutenberg. The web era has further automated the printing process. In order to make a show a further quantum leap has been necessary and this has been possible only with the help of Artificial Intelligence and Artificial Life Technique.

4 Appendix A – Real World Field Data

Object Data traffic from Object Server – 1 client – Worst case = First Logon

Object Data traffic from Object Server – 5 clients – Worst case = First Logon

Please note that the number of active (users) clients may be less than five at any given time.

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